

Casteism In Christinity of Paul Chirakkarode's Pulayathara

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Abstract

The novel *Pulayathara* is dalit literary works in Malayalam literature written by Paul chirakkarode in 2019. It is translated by Catherine Thankamma. Since 1990 there are a number of dalit literary works emerged in regional languages throughout india. The meaning of the word Dalit is broken or unprivileged. Dalit literary works frame out their culture, tradition, language and caste domination. Research works in dalit literature in the name of caste bring out depression and suppression of dalit people. The birth place of caste is in Hindu Religion since ancient time. The religion 'Hindu' stands for unequal among human. There are four caste hierarchies in Hindu Religion. And also untouchable, domination, and unrespectable is from Hindu religion. Dalit stands out from four caste hierarchy. So they are being called untouchable. After independence Mahatma Gandhi names 'Harijan' (God's Children) to untouchable. But the common term 'Dalit' for untouchable is everywhere in literary works and research area. In Dravidian political emerging movement Adidravitar. And now the term Dalit has been removed and named Scheduled caste by General government. The names for untouchable have been changed but in real life they do not have peaceful life. They have been fighting and agitating for their rights, respect and be away from domination having been happened by caste against them. So they are ready to be on other track. When Britishers colonize India dalit have associated with them. Britishers have respected them. So dalit decide to convert religion from Hindu to Christianity. The caste by which dalits' are not being treated respectfully and equally in Hindu religion is also happening in Christianity. Thus this paper deals with casteism in Christianity in the novel *Pulayathara*.

Key notes: Dalit, Unprivileged, Hierarchy, Dravidian, Untouchable, Adidravitar

Aim of the study

To bring out the caste discrimination which happened in Christianity in Paul Chirakkarode's *Pulayathara*.

Introduction

Literary works about dalit are rare in the past. Writers who belong to upper caste have written of dalit from their own perspective. They do not experience the life of dalit and their culture. Upper-caste writers will not expose deeply dalit's pain and caste discrimination in literature. Raj Gowthaman says that Im makkaḷai parriya tamiḷ eḷuttu ilakkiyam tōṇṇiya kalam toṭṭē uyarcaṭiyinaṇ paṭaitta ilakkiyaṅkaḷ yāvum paḷittup pēci vantullaṅa. Puṛaṇāṇūru im'maikaḷai iḷi piṛappālarkaḷ, kāviyaṅkaḷ ivarkaḷai poy, kaḷavu, pulāl, ākiyavarraṭaṅ campantap paṭuttip pēciṅa. Tēvāram pāṭiya appar ivarkaḷaiyum toḷu nōyarkaḷaiyum orē varicaiyil niṛuttinār (Talittiya vimarcaṅkaḷ kaṭṭuraikaḷ_11)

In Indian literature new seed have emerged throughout india In 1990. That seed has been called Dalit Literature in which humanism, equality, rights are mainly focused as well. Dalit literary works that have been written by dalit writers stand for their culture, tradition, and language. Many dalit novels

have been written by dalit writers at present.

In dalit novels the contradiction between upper-caste and dalit will be happening in Hindu religion. Hindu stands for inequity. Untouchable and domination are birth place of Hindu. Hindu society excludes dalit. Raj Gowthaman quotes Ayothidasar's words in his tamil book that Cātippiriviṅkaḷ, pārppaṇariṅ intu matattukkum uḷḷa campantam parriya avaratu purital, "intu matattukku cātip piriviṅkaḷ ātāram: Cātippiriviṅkaḷ kaḷukku intumatam-ātāram" (II_181) eṇṇu eḷutiṅār" (Talittiya vimarcaṅkaḷ kaṭṭuraikaḷ 170). Dr. Ambedkar says 'Hindu society as such does not exist. It is only a collection of caste'. (In Annihilation of Caste (the annotated critical edition-242) .So people who belong to any caste are called Hindus. Problems among hindus are stable. In Hindu society dalit have been dominated, lost their rights and have been treated inhuman. Dalit expect to make happy life.

In colonial period upper caste Hindus have been in touch with britishers. Many upper-caste people have followed Christianity. In the introduction of the novel *Pulayathara* translator, Catherine Thankamma, pointed out ' Many of the Syrian

traders were members of the Eastern Church. Some of them may have married local women and settled down in Kerala. Their descendants came to be called Syrian Christian.' (Pulayathara. Page-viii). There is a book

in tamil makātmā jōtirāv pulē in which Dananjay Keer notes that "Pampāyiliruntu kiṛistava paḷḷi āciryarkalīn tākkattāl pāpā patmaṅgi kiṛistava matattai taḷuviṅār"(makātmā jōtirāv pulē -93) He continues to list out whoever converted to Christianity. The conversion was also from upper-caste with the impact of Christianity "Makārājā tuḷip ciṅ kiṛistavattukku matam māriyatai parri intiya muḷukkavum kiṛistavarkaḷ urattu pēciṅārkaḷ. Mutalmutalil kiṛistavattai taḷuviya intiya iḷavaracaṅ ivarai. Aitarāpāt mākānattiliruntu tēcastā pārppaṅarāna ivar kiṛistava matattai taḷuviṅār"(makātmā jōtirāv pulē_94) To stay away from caste dalit decide to convert their religion. Raj Gowthaman says that "Maṅitarkaḷitaiyē pētam pārāṭṭāmal camattuvattai pōtitta kiṛistava matattukkum anta aḷavu talittukaḷ māriṅārkaḷ. (Talittiya vimarcaṅak kaṭṭuraikaḷ_172) During the colonial time dalit people have worked in the house of britishers. As being labours of britishers dalit have got education. Britishers do not follow untouchable over dalit. Britishers have treated them respectfully. So dalit joined to Christianity. Novels are very few about casteism even in Christianity. These are like Bama's *Karukku* Mark Stephan's *Mariyal*, Paul Chirakkarode's *Pulayathar*.

Paul chirakkarode is a dalit writer in Malayalam. He is an educator and human rights activist. He has written the novel *Pulayathara* which, is the title of the novel, holds two meaning. pulaya means pulayan (polen'e and pelen'e is regional in Malayalam). It is a caste name. In those days everyone was having the caste name after the name. Periyar strongly opposed and protested against this habit in tamil nadu. So Tamil Nadu is not in culture of adding caste after the name. Having caste after name is still in kerala and all over india. Tharacan variously mean platform, floor and home. In this novel parayan (r) is another untouchable caste name.

The main theme of the novel is to have a home. Living in own house is highly difficult to untouchable in the Indian caste

society. Dalit should work in landlord's house but do not earn anything for their life. In the beginning of the novel dalit live in the cow shelter into which human will not live. Only cow can be in the cow shelter. So dalit people are not even considered as human by upper caste.

Casteism in Christianity

The novel opens in the month of Makaram. People will start to work in paddy fields. Thevan pulayan is a farm worker in Narayana Nair's fields. Narayana Nair is landlord which means 'thampuran' in Malayalam. It is ironical that thampuran refers to both god and landlord. As thevan pulayan plans to build the house narayana nair asks him that "I will give you bamboo and palm leaves. In return I'll take twenty measures of paddy at the time of harvest. Remember that. Are you willing." (*Pulayathara*- page-5) Theven pulayan is not wealthy man to build own house. So he needs his thampura's help. Taking twenty measures of paddy is unfair to thevan pulayan. He and his son kandankoran decide to leave that place. But they do not know where to build the house.

Thevan pulayan and his son are arrived at pallithara pathros's house in Hilltop Land. Pallithara Pathros is a distant relative of thevan's. pallithara pathros lives in Mission land that belongs to Hilltop Church. As pallithara pathros was in hindu religion he got second marriage. So that he became an outcast. While being away from community he joined holy church with his new wife called maria. So he was called new Christian .dalit, converted to Christian, have been called new christian in Kerala. Before joining holy church their name was Kiliyan, Kunjzhaki. These were all Hindu name. dalit, before joining to christianity were in hindu religion. But as the view of Iyothee Thass dalits were following Buddham and Samanam in ancient time.

At the end of every month there will be the meeting in Hilltop Church along with the priest. At the end of the meeting they will have prayer. The priest's first choice to conduct the prayer is pallithara pathros. "with this desire I mind the priest asked, shall we send for preacher pathros?" (page-38) on hearing this order from the priest Custodian Thomas, main character in this novel, belongs to upper- caste, is trembled. He does not like that a dalit who stands on the stage and pray

for upper caste should not become a preacher. The same issue is also in hindu religion that no non-brahmin should be preacher of Hindu temple. With all efforts of custodian Thomas pathros was dropped as preacher. Stephen belongs to upper caste and has been invited for pray at the end of the meeting.

Custodian Thomas blames about communism. "satan, the roaring lion. do you know who that is, preacher? Who? Communism. It is about communism that the lord speaks in the Bible"(page-46-47). He is against dalit and communism. A Large numbers of dalit people become communist in kochumolumbram where dalit people are in crowd. Custodian Thomas does not like dalit so that he names communism as satan. In the book Marx and Ambedkar Continuing the Dialogue the authors give main point that dalit and communist shout work together in the political field. The reason is that the ideology of Marx and Ambedkar talks about freedom and equality.

Caste discrimination inside the church is about the sitting. Benches are available in the church only for upper caste. The author Paul Chirakkarode mentions two way of culture in praying god inside the church. Sitting on the benches is only for upper caste whereas dalit people will sit on the floor. "at the time of celebrating Christ's last supper, they would get up from these benches and kneel before the maduvaha. Once they received the holy eucharist, they would return to sit down again and relax". (page-55) in hindu religion dalit are not allowed to enter into the temple. The same is followed by upper caste in Christianity. To sit on the floor before upper caste inside the church dalit people feel as respectable. The only thing is that dalit people are allowed into the church to sit on the floor, not to sit on the benches. Raj Gowthaman

says that "1753 Ām āñṭiliruntē intukkaḷiṭam iruppataip pōla cāti vērupātu kiṛistava tēvālayattil iruntu pārampariya urimayai eṭuttuc sonṇārkaḷ" (talittiya vimarcanak kaṭṭuraikaḷ _190)

Hilltop land is Church missionary's property. Both dalit and upper caste have been residing there so far. If third man stays in the house of relatives who have built home in hilltop land, he/she must be converted to Christianity. Thevan Pulayan and his son kandankoran stay in Pathros's house. It is come to know to custodian, who orders to

pathros "you have grown that much, have you, pelen'e! roared Thomas. I will put an end to your audacity. you will not allow me to deal with you kindly! You cannot live on mission land and have a Hindu in your home. isn't that what I said in plain language".(Pulayathara -page-77) custodian is not a Priest of the church. He has no rights to threaten pathros. Allowing any relatives to stay at home is the wishes of pathros. If it is not fair culture of Hilltop land Priest must warn pathros for his mistakes. But custodian thinks him as a ruler of dalit.

Paul Chirakkarode clearly pointed out the character of upper caste men against dalit. Once again custodian was so angry of pathros's works. "pathros took a bundle of paddy sheaves and placed it in his puttil.....coustodian Thomas saw it at once he....angrily moved to pathros's side and said , what is that, pathros pelen'e?" (page-92). Dalit can work in their fields but they should not take anything from the land. Before taking anything dalit should ask in humble voice. Though Custodian Thomas is not in charge of the paddy field he controls pulayans. It is absolutely caste mind set. Paul Chirakkarode merely expresses what happen in real life.

"The upper -caste members of the church had still not acknowledged the new Christians as equals." (page -100). To find equality is highly difficult in Hindu religion. The same is also in Christianity. Christians in India and Tamil Nadu are called Natar Christian, Utayar Christians, Vanniyar Christians, Dalit Christians, Nair Christians, Pulayan and Parayar Christians. The high caste Hindus will not even touch the hands of dalit. The upper caste Christian will not accept new Christians (pulayans and parayars) as brothers. Once Hindus joined Christianity they should not hold caste name. But Ayothithasar says in tamil "Kiṛistavattil cātikku iṭamē illāta pōtu kiṛistava ceṭṭi kiṛistava nāṭār enṛellām kiṛistavareppaṭi taṅkaḷai aḷaikkalāmā"(mārks ampētkār toṭarum uraiyāṭal _195). It is the question of Ayothithasar

In order to marry anna kidathi kandankoran joined to Christianity. His name was also changed as Thoma. He married anna kidathi and tried to apply for home in Hilltop land. As he applied for home he was humiliated by upper-caste men in

front of everyone.

poocha kristyani! Thoma was stuned. He had every right to be shocked, didn't he? So what if pulayan receives the Christian faith, if the holy of holies baptism water falls on his forehead, if a cross is drawn on his forehead, if he gets a new name? all that does not change his pula, his untouchable status. (*Pulayathara* -page-115)

if a dalit who follows Christian faith he is being remained as untouchable. In Indian society a dalit may not get equal status. This is what paul chirakkarode brings out caste discrimination which happened in Christianity.

At the end of the novel paulos and outha pulayan try to conduct a meeting to explain brutality of caste even in Christianity. Custodian Thomas and other upper-caste men take hard efforts to stop the meeting. In spite of their goodness the meeting was successfully conducted. Paulos addresses to his people "we should. Now our people should make our own separate congregation. That achan (priest) can be the bishop." (page-172) finally dalit people decide to have their own priest and church. It is also in Hindu religion that only Brahmin will be the priest (Archagar). Later in Christianity the thing has been changed that all Christian from any caste become as priest.

The Syrian Christian starts to dilute the situation. So they blow the words of desire "would there be lords and slaves in the heavenly kingdom too? Would God Jehovah allow the lordly Christians and the slave Christians to sit together in that heaven? Thoma thought: Lies. all this is a big lie...it was all lies." (page 173). So New Christians are not ready to hear their words. They form a committee in which there will be the chief guest, the speaker, and a few others.

In Indian society People follow caste system. It is a constitutional right that a man can change his religion but not caste, which is by birth. Dalit have been facing more problems in the name of the caste. Dalit have misfortunes in Hindu religion. They are not considered as touchable human. So the conversion is only solution to them. It is the impact of Dr. Ambethkar who converted from Hindu to Buddhism with few words "we shall repair our mistakes now. I had the misfortune of being born with stigma of an untouchable. However, it is not my fault; but I will not die a Hindu, for this is my power." (In

Annihilation of Caste (the annotated critical edition-52)

Conclusion

Though Christianity is not holding caste system people who are converted to Christianity will follow casteism. It is the fact that religion will follow caste hierarchy, domination, discrimination and also untouchable. It may be any religion in India. If dalit follow any religion there will be the domination against them. Paul chirakkarode exploited in what way the caste happened in the Indian society and after the conversion dalit people are also mistreated and dominated by upper caste in Christianity.

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